

***Victoria amazonica* PETIOLES AS UNCONVENTIONAL EDIBLE PLANT: AN INORGANIC NUTRITION APPROACH**

Victoria amazonica Pecíolos como planta comestível não convencional:
Uma abordagem de nutrição inorgânica

Cláudia Cândida Silva¹
Sara Kethleen Soares de Loiola²
Patrícia de Souza Pinto Hidalgo³
Sergio Duvoisin Junior⁴
Valdely Ferreira Kinupp⁵

ABSTRACT

UEPs (Unconventional Edible Plant) are a promising source of plant nutrition and are an option in the face of changing dietary patterns as well as an option for plant foods that are potentially contaminated with pesticides. *Victoria amazonica* (waterlily) has been used as food by the Amazonian population and can be characterized as an UEP. In addition, this type of study can add economic value to Amazonian UEPs, bringing regional economic benefits, especially to rural communities with the highest UEP concentrations. The present study demonstrates the potential of *V. amazônica* petioles as food. Three petiole samples analyzed, each one in triplicate. The techniques of Wave Dispersion X-ray Fluorescence (WDXRF) and X-ray Diffraction (XRD) were used to identify the elements present in the samples and, when possible, to infer about the present compounds. The following chemical elements were observed in the samples studied: Sodium 0.7%, Magnesium 0.05%, Aluminum 0.02%, Silicon 0.05%, Phosphorus 0.1%, Sulfur 0.02%, Chlorine 0.6 %, Potassium 1.76%, Calcium 1.14%, Iron 0.01%. These are the most important elements. Fe is still treated as an antioxidant, a function observed in other studies. It was possible to identify potassium chloride in crystals obtained during the partitioning of the samples, suggesting a certain food functionality.

Key-words: *Victoria amazonica* (POEPP.) J.C. SOWERBY; Waterlily; X-Ray Fluorescence; X-Ray Diffraction.

RESUMO

As PANCs (Plantas Alimentícias Não Convencionais) são uma fonte promissora de nutrição vegetal e são uma opção diante das mudanças nos padrões alimentares, bem como uma opção para alimentos vegetais potencialmente contaminados com pesticidas. *Victoria amazonica* (lírio d'água) tem sido utilizada como alimento pela população amazônica e pode ser caracterizada como uma PANC. Além disso, este tipo de estudo pode agregar valor econômico às PANCs amazônicas, trazendo benefícios econômicos regionais, especialmente para as comunidades rurais com as maiores concentrações de PANCs. O presente estudo demonstra o potencial dos pecíolos de *V. amazônica* como alimento. Foram analisadas três amostras de pecíolo, cada uma em triplicata. As técnicas de Fluorescência de Raios-X por Dispersão de Ondas (WDXRF) e Difração de Raios-X (XRD) foram utilizadas para identificar os elementos presentes nas amostras e, quando possível, inferir sobre os compostos presentes. Nas amostras estudadas foram observados os seguintes elementos químicos: Sódio 0,7%, Magnésio 0,05%, Alumínio 0,02%, Silício 0,05%, Fósforo 0,1%, Enxofre 0,02%, Cloro 0,6%, Potássio 1,76%, Cálcio 1,14%, Ferro 0,01%. Estes são os elementos mais importantes. O Fe ainda é tratado como

¹ Doctor, UEA, claudiacsbr@gmail.com, <http://lattes.cnpq.br/6735185857453979>, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9852-1140>

² Master, UEA, sara.k.loiola@gmail.com, <http://lattes.cnpq.br/2372484526553680>, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1221-0382>

³ Doctor, UEA, phidalgo@uea.edu.br, <http://lattes.cnpq.br/3862324600810078>, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8042-1053>

⁴ Doctor, UEA, duvoisin66@hotmail.com, <http://lattes.cnpq.br/1737235899259374>, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2577-7898>

⁵ Doctor, IFAM, val@ifam.edu.br, <http://lattes.cnpq.br/1263334983122560>, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3892-7288>

antioxidante, função observada em outros estudos. Foi possível identificar cloreto de potássio nos cristais obtidos durante o particionamento das amostras, sugerindo certa funcionalidade alimentar.

Palavras-chave: *Victoria amazonica* (POEPP.) J.C. SOWERBY; Lírio d'água; Fluorescência de Raios-X; Difração de Raios-X.

1 INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of the food composition consumed in different regions of the world and Brazil is essential for a healthier and more careful diet, as opposed to the massification of a monotonous and unbalanced diet (Skoog; Hollerm; Nieman, 2002). To avoid incorrect decisions or conclusions, nutritional information needs to be reliable, updated, and as complete as possible, based on original analyses conducted in accordance with a representative sampling plan and validated methods, in order to truly represent the composition of the food (Skoog; Hollerm; Nieman, 2002).

There are two basic types of methods in food analysis: conventional and instrumental. The first are those that do not require any sophisticated equipment. Instrumental methods, as the name implies, are performed using more sophisticated electronic equipment. The choice of the analytical method depends on several factors. Relative quantity of the component to be studied: the components can be classified as major (more than 1%), where conventional methods are more applicable; minor (0.01–1%) and micro (less than 0.01%) and traces (ppm and ppb), with the application of more sensitive and sophisticated techniques; in relation to the total weight of the sample (Skoog; Hollerm; Nieman, 2002). Classical methods can achieve an accuracy of 99.9% when a compound analyzed is found in more than 10% of the sample. For components present in quantities less than 10%, the accuracy drops significantly, and then the choice of method must rely on instruments (Burgess, 2000). Chemical composition of the sample: the presence of interfering substances is very common in food. Thus, the choice of method depends directly on its chemical composition (Skoog *et al.*, 2006). Available resources: it is often not possible to use the best method of analysis due to its high cost, which can be limited depending on the type of equipment, data collection time, or even the type of reagent and specialized personnel (Zenebon; Pascuet; Tiglea, 2008).

When it comes to the analysis of inorganic nutrients in food, the most used techniques are atomic spectrometry. These require pre-processing of the samples that lead to their destruction, in addition to providing cross-contamination and loss of volatile elements (Association of official analytical chemist, 2000; Okada *et al.*, 2007; Santos *et al.*, 2008).

Wave Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (WDXRF) is a non-destructive technique that analyzes solids and liquids directly. Although it presents the disadvantage of not reaching detection limits

comparable to those of atomic spectrometry techniques, it has great advantages such as simplicity, safety, low cost, minimal use of reagents and glassware, generates little or no residue, and eliminates the sample decomposition step (Pataca; Bortoleto; Bueno, 2005; Bueno *et al.*, 2005).

As an example, we can mention the case in which Ruiz, Cordoba and Gonzales (1991) applied this technique to determine chlorine, phosphorus, and sulfur in food samples, including rice. The total analysis time for the determination of the analytes was less than 20 minutes per sample, and quantification was done using the analyte addition technique.

Unconventional Food Plants (known by the acronym UFP) are plants with food potential and spontaneous development; however, they are not consumed on a large scale or are used only in certain regions. UFPs can also be considered parts that are generally not consumed in common plants, such as the sweet potato leaf and the heart of the banana tree. An example is the Vitória-régia; its flowers, seeds, and petioles are used as food, although few people know this (Kinupp; Lorenzi, 2014).

UFPs are usually grown only by small producers and on a domestic scale. They range from native and unusual plants to exotic and wild ones with direct and indirect food uses such as vegetables, greens, fruits, nuts, oils, starch cereals, and even condiments and natural dyes (Kinupp, 2009).

Considered excellent sources of nutrients, vitamins, and minerals, UFPs also have characteristics that confer antioxidant, anti-inflammatory properties, and therapeutic action. The consumption of such plants and vegetables must be carried out respecting their characteristics and preparation methods to obtain such effects safely. It is also necessary to deepen the knowledge and conduct more studies about the possible presence of toxic phytochemicals or antinutritional factors that some UFPs may present if consumed inappropriately (Paschoal; Souza, 2015).

Another well-known plant is Ora-pro-nóbis (*Pereskia aculeata* Mill.), found in the Brazilian Southeast region. It contains calcium, magnesium, vitamin A, vitamin B9, vitamin C, tryptophan, zinc, and fiber, and has great protein potential. This UFP contains oxalate in its composition and must be prepared at high temperatures to inhibit its activity (Kinupp, 2009).

V. amazonica belongs to the Nymphaeaceae Salisbury family. It is an annual, robust, emergent herbaceous aquatic plant, fixed to the substrate, with up to 24 contemporary floating leaves, with a circular blade up to 2 meters in diameter, petaled, with raised margins and externally covered with very sharp spines, as well as the lower part of the blade, petiole, and flower. It is found in calm waters with temperatures around 26 to 30 °C, originating in the equatorial region of the Amazon River Basin. It has a solitary flower, with white petals up to 40 cm in diameter, lightly placed on the water surface,

opening at night with the release of an intense perfume. It has bacaceous fruit, dehiscent, underwater, with many thorns. In addition, it has seeds with abundant perisperm (Kinupp; Lorenzi, 2014; Pott; Pott, 2000).

The petiole is part of the basic constitution of the external morphology of the leaves and generally has a cylindrical shape. It connects the lamina to the stem through the base. The petiole can also be attached to the base or the middle of the lamina (Pott; Pott, 2000).

Some studies demonstrate the chemical properties of *Victoria amazonica*. Among these, the study of the relationship between the composition of flavonoids and the color variation of the flower (Wii *et al.*, 2018) describes 14 evaluated and quantified flavonoids, which include 3 anthocyanins and 10 flavonols. The study found that with the increase of anthocyanin content during flowering days, the colors of the flowers change over time. In addition, the different compositions of flavonoids result in different colors between the internal and external petals.

Another article evaluated the secondary metabolites of *V. amazonica* leaves from methanolic extracts collected in Chiayi, Taiwan (Chang *et al.*, 2014). The chemical constituents of the plants were separated by column chromatography. As a result, the isolation of 15 compounds is mentioned, including six steroids: β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, sitostenone, stigmasta-4,22-dien-3-one, 6β -hydroxy- β -sitosterone, and 6β -hydroxystigmasterone; four phenolic carboxylic acids: caffeic, p-hydroxybenzoic, protocatechuic, and vanillic acid; and five chlorophylls: pheophytin a, pheophorbide methyl ester, methyl-132-hydroxy-(132-S)-phosphorhide b, 132-hydroxy-(132-S)-fophisiina a, and aristofila c.

There are no studies that demonstrate the chemical properties of *V. amazonica* petioles; however, the aforementioned studies of flowers and leaves demonstrate their chemical potential for substances that may contribute to characterizing it as a functional food.

There are several uses of *V. amazonica* in cooking, which include various parts of the plant. From using its seeds as popcorn or processed to make flours and other products, even tender petals can be used for raw salads, sautéed, stewed, or used for canapés. The petals can also be crystallized or used for desserts. Petioles, in turn, can be used as vegetables (Kinupp; Lorenzi, 2014).

This work aimed to apply X-ray techniques in the study of UFPs to characterize the inorganic part of the petioles of *V. amazonica*, aiming at its use as food.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

As it is a plant with easy access for collection, good distribution in the Amazon region, and already consumed by local populations, the species mentioned was chosen for this study.

The *V. amazonica* plants used in this study were collected from a farm located on the coast of the Terra Nova district, in the municipality of Careiro da Várzea, Amazonas. The identification was carried out by botanist Dr. Valdely Kinupp, and the voucher specimen was deposited in the Herbarium of the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Amazonas – EAFM.

After identification, the petioles were subjected to drying for subsequent grinding. The process began with the preparation of the petioles, which were washed and peeled, then dried in an oven at a temperature of 45 °C for 72 hours. The material was then crushed in a knife mill.

2.1 Ash Content

The proximate composition analyses were carried out in the laboratory of the Chemical Research Group Applied to Technology at the State University of Amazonas.

To determine the ash content, a previously calcined and tared crucible was used, in which 2.000 g of the sample was weighed. Incineration was performed in stages, starting with heating on an electric plate. Once the smoke ceased, the crucible was transferred to a muffle furnace at 550 °C for 3 hours. The mass was then determined (Moretto *et al.*, 2002). The calculation for determining ash content follows Equation 01:

$$\% \text{ ash} = (100 \times N) / P$$

Where:

N = Mass in grams of ash

P = Mass in grams of the sample

2.2 Material Characterization by WDXRF

The X-ray fluorescence analysis was performed at the State University of Amazonas. For a 2.0 g sample of dried petiole, Wave Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence (WDXRF) analysis was conducted by the Crowfoot Group of X-Ray Methods, using Rigaku equipment, Supermini model, capable of analyzing elements with atomic numbers between 11 and 92 (Perring; Andrey, 2003; Da-Col; Bueno; Melquiades, 2015).

All data were obtained using a set of analyzer crystals (LiF, PET, and RX25), with 250 seconds of exposure time and a voltage of 40 keV. All measurements were carried out under vacuum, with a spinning sampler, in triplicate, and readings were taken on intermittent days (Leyden, 1984).

The characteristic X-ray radiation of the $K\alpha$ -line and the background radiation were measured for the determination of each element, while concentration was based on their relative intensities (cps/ μ A) using external standards (Araújo *et al.*, 2003).

2.3 Obtaining the Crystals

The extract was subjected to partitioning with solvents of different polarities. Initially, a 4.0000 g sample of the methanolic extract was solubilized in methanol, where crystal formation was observed. These crystals were collected and submitted to ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR analysis, which confirmed the absence of carbon and hydrogen, indicating that the substance was not organic. Therefore, Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed by the Crowfoot Group of X-Ray Methods.

2.4 Crystal Characterization by XRD

Data collection was carried out at the Federal Institute of Amazonas – IFAM, Manaus Distrito Industrial Campus. To observe the crystalline phases present in the crystals obtained through sample partitioning, the Powder X-Ray Diffraction technique was used. The equipment was configured with a 0.6 mm slit, 3 mm knife, Cu radiation tube ($K\alpha = 0.15406$ nm, 30 kV, 10 mA), scanning range of $5\text{--}100^\circ$ (2θ), step size of 0.02° , with intensities recorded for 1 second at each step. Phases were identified using X'Pert High Score Plus software. The crystals were powdered to ensure random orientation of the molecules, providing a sufficient number of crystals to generate detectable signals from all respective angles of all components present in the sample. Maximum peak intensities are often used to estimate the quantity of specific crystalline phases (Bertin, 1975).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Encouraging the use of UFPs in everyday food does not necessarily mean replacing conventional ingredients with non-conventional ones, but rather incorporating new flavors, textures, and nutrients into already established preparations. Their use is often related to the lifestyle and cultural identity of traditional populations, with preparation and consumption carried out in

characteristic ways across diverse meals. Each plant is an ingredient with its own peculiarities and applications (Kinupp; Lorenzi, 2014).

To support the consumption of these vegetables, a series of scientific studies have been conducted to ensure constant updates to the registry of food species, enabling greater knowledge about their nutritional properties and the safety of their use (KINUPP, 2009). Among these studies, the most common and relevant were performed in this work.

3.1 Ashes content

The values obtained for the ash parameter, which is part of the proximate composition of fresh *V. amazonica* petioles, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Values obtained for the proximate composition of *Victoria amazonica* petioles.

Parameter	g / 100g of fresh sample of petioles of <i>V. amazonica</i>
Ashes	0.64

Source: Osman (2010).

Osman (2010), in his study on the life cycle, leaf structure, and morphoanatomical variations influenced by environmental differences for *Victoria amazonica* (Poepp.) J.C. Sowerby (Nymphaeaceae) in Central Amazon, compares the proximate composition of roots and rhizomes in mixed and floodplain water environments. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Average composition of roots and rhizome of *Victoria amazonica* in 100g, comparing the floodplain and mixed water environments.

Parameter	Ashes (g/100g)
Roots (mixed waters)	0.60±0,99
Roots (Várzea)	0.98±0,29
Rhizome (mixed waters)	1.03±0,18
Rhizome (floodplain)	3.42±0,45

Source: Osman (2010).

The study confirms that the environment influences the centesimal composition of the plant. The distribution of nutrients in the soil and phytomass of floodplain and igapó environments differs. The results for the petiole of *V. amazonica* are close to those described for roots and rhizomes.

Both, Osman’s study and the present work attests to the plant’s capacity to store nutrients, which can be enhanced by its highly developed root system and adaptive characteristics, as the species colonizes mixed and floodplain water environments.

3.2 Analysis by WDXRF

The Wavelength Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence (WDXRF) analysis, performed by the Crowfoot Group of X-Ray Methods, revealed the mass proportion of constituents in the petiole sample, as shown in Figure 1.

Graphic 1: X-ray fluorescence analysis in *Victoria amazonica* petioles.

Source: Research data (2020).

According to plant physiology, nineteen chemical elements are essential for most plants. Essentiality involves three criteria: (i) the plant cannot complete its life cycle without the element; (ii) the element’s function is specific and irreplaceable; (iii) the element is a necessary component of an essential metabolite. These elements are classified as macroelements (C, H, O, N, P, S, Ca, Mg, Si, K) and microelements (Fe, B, Mn, Cl, Na, Ni, Cu, Zn, Mo) (Taiz; Zeiger, 2004).

Ten chemical elements were observed in the samples:

- *Macroelements:* Mg, Si, P, S, K, Ca
- *Microelements:* Na, Cl, Fe
- *Non-essential:* Al

Sodium, potassium, and chlorine were found in higher concentrations, iron and aluminum in lower concentrations.

Sulfur is well distributed throughout plant tissues and organs, as a component of proteins, vitamins, and coenzyme A, which participates in the Krebs cycle. Among the essential elements detected, sulfur can be found in concentrations ranging from 0.69% to 1.17% (m/m).

K, Mg, Cl, and Na are nutrients found in ionic forms in plants. K, Mg, and Cl have greater translocation capacity, but only Na and Mg were exuded in significant quantities (Taiz; Zeiger, 2004; Almeida *et al.*, 2002; Meyer *et al.*, 1983).

Fe is involved in redox reactions and has low translocation capacity, similar to Ca, which is fixed in cell walls (Salisbury; Ross, 1992).

Comparing the data obtained here with the centesimal composition, there is strong agreement. Total ash is 0.64% of the material studied. During calcination, lighter elements associated with volatile compounds are lost. Elements like K, Cl, and Mg are lost this way. In X-ray fluorescence, the sample is analyzed in natura. Removing these elements from the mass percentage sum yields the observed ash value.

Although the Nymphaeaceae group is relatively well studied, most works focus on botanical aspects or organic substances. The exception is Osman (2010), which serves as a comparative basis.

Sodium, potassium, and chlorine were found in greater concentrations. Osman (2010) also observed potassium values of 1.04% in flowers and 1.29% in leaves of *V. amazonica*.

Considering the nutritional potential of *V. amazonica* petioles, potassium and sodium values are noteworthy. For humans, potassium is an essential macronutrient. It is the main intracellular cation and plays roles in acid-base balance, osmotic pressure regulation, nerve impulse conduction, muscle contraction, and cell membrane function. According to the Institute of Medicine (2005), adults should consume at least 4.7 grams of potassium daily to lower blood pressure, mitigate salt effects, and reduce risks of kidney stones and bone loss. However, most American women aged 31–50 consume less than half the recommended amount, and men only slightly more. Healthy adults aged 19–50 should consume 1.5 grams of sodium daily to replace average losses and maintain essential nutrient intake.

3.3 Crystals Characterization by XRD

Partitioning the methanolic extract into fractions of different polarities allowed crystal formation in the alcoholic fraction. These crystals were analyzed by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), performed by the Crowfoot Group of X-Ray Methods. The data are shown in Figure 2.

Graphic 2: X-ray Diffraction analysis of *Victoria amazonica* petiole crystals.

Source: Research data (2020).

Based on the analysis, the crystals were identified as inorganic potassium chloride. These findings align with WDXRF data, where K and Cl were the most abundant elements.

According to the Food Guide for the Brazilian Population (Brasil, 2006), 800 mg of Na and 1,400 mg of K should be consumed in each of the three main meals. The World Health Organization (2006) recommends a maximum daily intake of 2,000 mg of Na and a minimum of 3,500 mg of K. Comparing these recommendations with our results, the petiole of *V. amazonica* can help meet these needs in a healthy way, as its salty flavor derives not only from NaCl but also from KCl. This mixture is commercially known as “light salt” and is recommended for hypertensive individuals.

4 CONCLUSION

All observed chemical elements are essential for plants and humans, with the exception of Al. All have also been widely observed in other Amazonian plants and waters.

The analysis of X-Ray Fluorescence and X-Ray Diffraction showed that the petiole is a source of sodium and potassium chloride, important elements for the proper functioning of the organism.

The combination of these three techniques (total ash, WDXRF, and XRD) supports the results obtained by the others, clearly showing the quantity of minerals, the inorganic elements that make up the ash, and their losses due to volatility, providing a more solid and broad picture for discussions about nutrition.

5 FUNDING

This work is grateful for funding from FAPEAM.

REFERENCES

Almeida, M. M. B. *et al.* Determinação de nutrientes minerais em plantas medicinais. **Food Science and Technology**, Campinas, 22, 94, Jan. 2002. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/cta/a/CVSQ-KfLtzny9gqW3KsTLkNs/?format=html&lang=pt>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Araújo, M. F. *et al.* Elemental composition of marine sponges from the Berlengas natural park, western Portuguese coast. **X-Ray Spectrometry**, 32, 428, Set. 2003. Disponível em: <https://analyticalsciencejournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/xrs.660>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Association of Official Analytical Chemist (AOAC). **Official Methods of Analysis**. Washington D.C: AOAC International, 2000. Disponível em: <https://academic.oup.com/aoac-publications/book/-/45491>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Bertin, E. P. **Principles and Practice of X-Ray Spectrometric Analysis**. Plenum Publishing Corporation: New York, USA. 1975.

Brasil. Ministério da Saúde. **Guia alimentar para a população brasileira: promovendo a alimentação saudável**. Brasília: Ministério da Saúde; Brasília, DF: Editora MS, 2006. Disponível em: <https://www.nescon.medicina.ufmg.br/biblioteca/imagem/0290.pdf>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Bueno, M. I. M. S. *et al.* X-ray scattering processes and chemometrics for differentiating complex samples using conventional EDXRF equipment. **Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems**, 78, 96, Jul. 2005. Disponível em: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016974390500002X>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Burgess, C. **Valid Analytical Methods and Procedures**. County Durham, UK: The Royal Society of Chemistry; 2000.

Chang, M. Y. *et al.* Metabólitos secundários das folhas de *Victoria amazonica*. **Chemistry of Natural Compounds** 50, 5, 955. Disponível em: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10600-014-1131-5>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Institute Of Medicine (IOM). **Dietary Reference Intakes For Water, Potassium, Sodium, Chloride, and Sulfate**. Washington, DC: National Academy Press, 2005.

Kinupp, V. F. **Plantas alimentícias não-convencionais (UFPs): uma riqueza negligenciada**. In: REUNIÃO ANUAL DA SBPC–MANAUS, 61, 2009, Manaus. ANAIS DA 61ª REUNIÃO ANUAL DA SBPC–MANAUS. Manaus: Instituto Federal de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia do Amazonas. Disponível em: https://www.sbpcnet.org.br/livro/61ra/mesas_redondas/MR_ValdelyKinupp.pdf. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Kinupp, V. F.; Lorenzi, H. (Org). **Plantas alimentícias não convencionais (UFP) no Brasil: guia de identificação, aspectos nutricionais e receitas ilustradas**. São Paulo: Instituto Plantarum de Estudos da Flora, 2014.

Leyden, D. E. **Fundamentals of X-Ray Spectrometry as Applied to Energy Dispersive Techniques**. Mountain View: California, USA. (1984).

Meyer, B. *et al.* **Introdução à Fisiologia Vegetal**. Coimbra, Portugal: Atlantida Editora, 1983.

Moretto, E. *et al.* **Introdução a ciência dos alimentos**. Florianópolis: Editora da UFSC, 2002.

Okada, I. A. *et al.* Validation and application of an analytical method for determining inorganic nutrients in milled rice. **Food Science and Technology**. 27, 39, 492, Set. 2007. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/cta/a/cLRPy84NQvXcW9hcYZMWx7P/?format=pdf&lang=pt>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Osman, S. M. R. **Ciclo de vida, estrutura foliar e variações morfoanatômicas influenciadas por diferenças ambientais para *V. amazonica* (POEPP.) J.C. Jowerby (Nymphaeaceae) na Amazônia Central**. Manaus, 2010. Disponível em: <https://repositorio.inpa.gov.br/handle/1/12810>. Acessado em Out. 2025.

Paschoal, V.; Souza, N. S. Plantas Alimentícias não convencionais (UFP). *In*: Chaves, D. F. S. (Ed.). **Nutrição Clínica Funcional: compostos bioativos dos alimentos**. Salvador, BA: VP Editora; 2015.

Pataca, L. C. M.; Bortoleto, G. G.; Bueno, M. I. M. S. Determinação de arsênio em águas contaminadas usando fluorescência de raios-x por Energia dispersiva. **Química Nova**. 8, 4, 579, Ago. 2005. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/qn/a/Dt4hLkFgbvhSZkQtBkLH9cM/?lang=pt>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Da-Col, J. A.; Bueno, M. I. M. S.; Melquiades, F. L. Fast and Direct Na and K Determination in Table, Marine, and Low-Sodium Salts by X-ray Fluorescence and Chemometrics. **Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry**. 63, 9, Fev. 2015. Disponível em: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jf504941z>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Perring, L.; Andrey, D. ED-XRF as a tool for rapid minerals control in milk-based products. **Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry**. 51, 15, Jun. 2003. Disponível em: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jf034158p>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Pott, V. J.; Pott, A. **Plantas aquáticas do Pantanal**. Embrapa: Centro de Pesquisa Agropecuária do Pantanal (Corumbá-MS); Brasília: Embrapa Comunicação para Transferência de Tecnologia; 2000. Disponível em: <https://livimagens.sct.embrapa.br/amostras/00066170.pdf>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Ruiz, T. P.; Cordoba, M. H.; Gonzalez, R. O. A Rapid Method for the Determination of Chlorine, Phosphorus, and Sulfur in Flours of Grains and Legumes using Wavelength Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrometry **J. Assoc. Offic. Anal. Chem.** Vol. 74, n. 4, p. 625. Ago. 1991. Disponível em: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1917809/>. Acessado em Out. 2025

Salisbury, F. B.; Ross, C. W. **Plant Physiology**. Belmont, California: Wadsworth Publishing Co., 1992.

Santos, W. P. C. *et al.* Use of Doehlert design for optimizing the digestion of beans for multi-element determination by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry. **Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society**.; 19, 1, 1, Mar. 2008. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/jbchs/a/LRz4KCSpyknkXzSKCnHb7QD/?format=html&lang=en>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Skoog, D. A. *et al.* **Fundamentos de Química Analítica**. Tradução da 8ª Edição norte-americana. São Paulo-SP: Editora Thomson; 2006.

Skoog, D. A.; Holler, F. J.; Nieman, T. A. **Princípios de Análise Instrumental**. 5ª edição. São Paulo, SP: Editora Bookman, 2002.

Taiz, L.; Zeiger, E. **Fisiologia Vegetal**. 3rd ed., São Paulo, SP: Bookman, 2004.

Wii, Q. *et al.* Relations between the flavonoid composition and flower color variation in Victoria. **Plant Biology**; 20, 4, 674, Jul. 2018. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1111/plb.12835>. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

World Health Organization (WHO). **Reducing salt intake populations: report of a WHO forum and technical meeting**. Paris, France; 2006. Disponível em: https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/sci/med-staff/cappuccio/publications/who_2007_salt_report.pdf. Acessado em: Out. 2025.

Zenebon, O.; Pascuet, N. S.; Tiglia, P. **Métodos físico-químicos para análise de alimentos**. Instituto Adolfo Lutz, São Paulo, 2008.